

ENHANCING INDONESIAN STUDENTS PERFORMANCE IN CHINA: ROLE OF STUDENT MOTIVATION, PERSONAL RELATIONSHIP, DISCIPLINE AND STUDENT SATISFACTION

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Abstract

One of the essential parts of Chinese higher education is studying abroad for academic purposes, which is also a crucial component of developing talents through higher education. It plays a significant role in Chinese students' educational experiences abroad. It is also a crucial component for other national students studying in China. Education has become an important area and a turning point for international exchanges between China and other nations as a result of the establishment of various fields and regions. The objective of this study is to identify the role of an education agency for Indonesian students enrolled in Higher Education Institutions in China. The 133 respondents who are students studying in China participated in the study and were examined using the SEM-PLS 3.0 analysis tool. This study discovered that student satisfaction has an impact on mediating the effects of student motivation, interpersonal relationships, discipline, and performance on students.

Keywords: Student Motivation; Relationship; Discipline; Satisfaction; Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental components of Chinese higher education is studying abroad for academic purposes, which is also a crucial component of developing talent through higher education. It plays a significant role in Chinese students' education abroad. To enhance communication and understanding between China and the outside world, this is crucial.

The advancement of educational research has been in line with China's economic and social development. From a political perspective, the Chinese government has placed a high value on studying in China since the founding of the People's Republic of China and sees it as a valuable source of information, a valuable resource, and a useful avenue for exchanging cultures with other countries. New paragraph: use this style when you need to begin a new paragraph. Education has emerged as a key area and a turning point for exchanges between China and developed nations as a result of the opening up of numerous fields and regions. One indication of its significance is the increasing speed of Chinese academic development. As China's economy, trade, science, and technology have advanced, as well as its culture and educational system, colleges and universities have begun to enlist self-funded international students.

China has overtaken Japan as Asia's top study destination in 2020, moving up from fourth place globally. Over 500,000 foreign students are estimated to be enrolled in academic programs in China[1]. Nearly every country and area have access to student resources, including the more

than 15,000 Indonesian students studying in China, many of whom get financial aid in the form of scholarships. The five major categories of scholarships offered to overseas students by pertinent Chinese institutions are as follows. The CNY Education Co., Ltd. (CNY) recommends a lot of Indonesian students to study in China, and many of them benefit from this scholarship.

The consequences of the Covid-19 epidemic, however, forced as many as 546 Indonesian students to delay their graduation in 2021[2]. Due to the pandemic, Indonesian students' interest in China has decreased, which is related to the reason that was just said and affects both student performance and interest. according to a survey that was given to up to 50,452 Indonesian students in 2022. However, fewer students chose China as their study abroad location than Australia, where 13,880 students opt to go. China was the only country having an order of 14 among all pupils who turned into responses [3]. Student performance is a measure used in this study to assess government initiatives that offer chances to Indonesian students through the CNY institution. A pre-survey was administered to 50 students to determine the variables that affect student performance, and the results are as follows:

Table 1: Pre-survey Questionnaire

No	Factors Affecting Students Performance	Answer	
		Yes	No
1.	Academic & Education Quality	45	5
2.	Work	40	10
3.	Career & Migration	38	12
4.	Student Motivation	22	28
5.	Teacher Behavior	29	21
6.	Personal Relationship	21	29
7.	Processes (Convenience, Speed, Clarity)	25	25
8.	Discipline	24	26
9.	Student Satisfaction	22	28
10.	Government Services	29	21

Source : Research Data (2022)

The results of the table above show that 28 students said that student motivation did not significantly impact performance; this shows that student motivation is still relatively low. Students struggle greatly with a lack of drive. Therefore, understanding the reasons for low motivation in students as well as how to cope with them are crucial undertakings. In addition to these findings, 29 students said that their interpersonal interactions did not impair their academic performance while studying in China, and 26 more claimed that discipline did not affect their academic performance. In the end, 26 students responded that they were not affected by their level of satisfaction in their academic achievement, indicating that this is still the case in China for Chinese students.

According to the results of the initial survey, the variables related to student motivation, interpersonal relationships, and discipline are classified as exogenous or independent variables. The student satisfaction variable, which is also an endogenous variable or the dependent

variable along with the students performance variable, is positioned as a mediating variable. In modern higher education, it is crucial to understand the connection between student performance and satisfaction. Other than the previously mentioned significant relationship, this relationship is receiving a lot of attention from academics and teaching professionals because it may strengthen the potent synergies already at play in students' educational experiences. Student retention, student attraction, and good word-of-mouth marketing are all influenced by student happiness, which has grown to be a significant burden for universities. Student satisfaction is the primary source of competitive advantage[4].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

2.1. Literature Review

A crucial component of the organization is its human resources. Whatever its shape and purpose, an organization's foundation rests on numerous human-benefiting concepts and relies on individuals to carry out its goal. Human resource management, also known as human resource organization and management, is the process of organizing and managing human resources in accordance with the corporate vision in order to fulfill organizational goals. Human resource management is a science that focuses on finding ways to empower individuals within an organization, establish positions, work groups, and develop employees with the necessary skills. It also looks for ways to improve employee performance and reward employees for their efforts[50]. Human resource management, on the other hand, is the process of hiring, developing, evaluating, and rewarding people as well as for managing labor relations, health and safety, and legal issues [6]. Based on the previously provided human resource explanation, it can be stated that human resource management is an effort to raise the standard of workers' work in order for them to successfully complete organizational objectives.

2.1.1. Student Motivation

The term "motivation" refers to a force, either internal or external to a person, that inspires excitement and perseverance to pursue particular behaviors [7]. Furthermore, after adjusting for high school GPA as their primary conventional predictor, the overall score of motivational regulation techniques and the most particular strategies strongly predicted both the analyzed elements of academic performance [8]. Since higher education is a crucial component of any nation's economy, it can be claimed that both public and private institutions are primarily interested in this area. The globalization of higher education results in an internationalization of institutions and students. International students are migrating abroad increasingly frequently to seek their education as well as other interests including employment possibilities, cultural and social experiences, and even migration[9]. Based on this argument the dimensions of student motivation used in this study are: (1) Academic & Education Quality (2) Work (3) Career & Migration (4) Pleasure & Experience.

2.1.2. Student Satisfaction

An evaluation of students' educational experiences, services, and facilities might result in a short-term attitude that is known as student satisfaction. Prior to the development of higher education-specific satisfaction models, it was assessed using frameworks for measuring general satisfaction. Students' contentment as a temporary attitude that results from an assessment of their educational experiences [10]

Student satisfaction is the most important competitive advantage and that it also contributes to student engagement, student attractiveness for new students, and positive word-of-mouth communication. Student satisfaction has become a significant concern for universities.[4]. Fieger identified the following elements that promote academic satisfaction: (1) Teaching (2) Assessment (3) Generic Skills and Learning Experiences.[11]. A number of research have been done on student motivation and student satisfaction [12][13][14][15][16][17].The results confirmed that students' motivation significantly had positive effects on students' satisfaction. As these studies' findings suggest that there is a positive and significant correlation between student motivation and student satisfaction, the following is a proposed hypothesis for the study:

H1: Student Motivation has a significant effect on Student Satisfaction.

2.1.3. Personal Relationship

Achieving shared objectives requires frequent and considerable engagement between lecturer and students. Students may or may not appreciate it, but each lecturer exhibits unique habits that set him apart from his counterparts. On the other hand, some lecturers have a strong preference for or against a certain student's behavior [18]. Personal relationships have the following dimensions: (1) Influence (Dominance Submission) and (2) Proximity (Opposition Cooperation)[19]. On personal relationships and student satisfaction, several studies have been conducted [20][21][22][23][24]. These researches came to the conclusion that there is a positive and significant relationship between interpersonal relationships and student satisfaction. Consequently, we provide the following hypothesis in this study:

H2. Personal Relationship has a significant effect on Student Satisfaction

2.1.4. Discipline

Particular fields of knowledge, study, and education are frequently referred to as disciplines. Discipline is the process of instructing or training someone. Discipline and the training process that is carried out by individuals who give direction and guidance during instructional activities are closely related. Discipline is a way of thinking, acting and behaving which includes following the rules—written or unwritten—at all times. The understanding and readiness to abide by all applicable laws and social standards are also aspects of discipline. As long as a student is enrolled in school, their responsibility, attitude, conduct, and action in conformity with all types of regulation may be used to judge their level of student discipline[25]. The four dimensions of discipline, are: (1) Focus; (2) Intention; (3) Responsibility; and (4) Structure. Numerous research on discipline and student satisfaction have been carried out [26][27] and it

has been found that discipline has a positive and significant impact on students' satisfaction. This led this study to suggest the following hypothesis:

H3. Discipline has a significant effect on Student Satisfaction

2.1.5. Student Performance

For learning environments including universities and colleges, predicting students' performance is one of the most crucial topics since it assists in the development of effective processes that, among other things, promote academic achievement and minimize dropout. These benefit from the standardization of several student-related tasks that deal with large amounts of data collected through software tools for technology-enhanced learning. As a consequence, scientific analysis and processing of these data can provide us with knowledge about the students' knowledge and how it relates to learning achievement [28]. There are two elements that influence student performance, including the following: (1) Internal factors which originates from inside the students themselves, is the first element to have an impact on student performance. Students' physiological or physical health, interest in learning, level of intelligence or intelligence, drive to study, abilities, and interests are among the internal elements. (2) External factors are those that have an impact on students' performance but are unrelated to the students themselves. The school's curriculum, teaching strategies, ways of enforcing discipline, facilities for teaching and learning, student grouping systems, social systems that are common in the school environment, and interactions between teachers, staff, and students are all types of external variables. The country's political and economic situation, as well as geographic and climatic circumstances, are described lastly.

Student performance refers to aptitude, success, or motivation to do assignments. The performance of individuals in achieving certain objectives or goals. There are three dimensions to analyze student performance: (1) Intellectual Behaviors (2) Interpersonal Behaviors (3) Intrapersonal behavior.[29]. Numerous prior researchers have been interested in the relationship between student motivation and performance [30][31][32][33][34], Accordingly, the following theory is put out in this study:

H4. Student Motivation has a significant effect on Student Performance

The relationship between personal relationships and academic performance has been the subject of several research [35][36][37][38][39], then all these researchers arrived to the same conclusion: personal relationships matter and have a positive impact on academic performance. Consequently, we suggest the following hypothesis for this study:

H5. Personal Relationship has a significant effect on Student Performance

The effect of discipline on student performance has been a subject of previous researchers [40][41][42] and researchers came to the conclusion that discipline has a significant and positive impact on students' academic achievement. Therefore, the following hypothesis is put out in this study:

H6. Discipline has a significant effect on Student Performance

Previous research has examined into the relationship between student satisfaction and performance [43][44][45][46][47][48]. The researchers concluded that student happiness is closely related to student performance, hence the following hypothesis is proposed in this study:

H7. Student Satisfaction has a significant effect on Student Performance

According to the findings of earlier study, the research framework is as follows:

2.2. Methodology

Indonesian students from eleven Chinese universities provided the data for this study (Eastern, Central and Western China). A questionnaire was given out by researchers in the second half of 2022, and a total of 133 students responded. In this study, Partial Least Squares was the method of data analysis (PLS). A structural equation model (SEM) with an approach based on variance- or element structural equation modelling is PLS. Researchers that concentrate on the social sciences frequently utilize SEM because it provides a better degree of flexibility in research that links theory and data together and can perform path analysis with latent variables[49]

3. RESULT

According to data from 133 respondents, women made up 60.9% of the sample, while those between the ages of 18 and 30 made up 70.1% of the sample.

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Category	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	52	39,1
	Woman	81	60,9
	Total	133	100,0
Age	18 - 30 years old	94	70,1
	31 - 40 years old	39	29,9
	Total	133	100,0

Source: Research Data (2022)

Based on the outer loading values derived from data processing using SEM-PLS, which are displayed in the following table, all indicators included in this study have been demonstrated to be valid.

Table 3: Outer Loading

Item	Outer Loading
SM1-1 I decided to come to China to obtain a good education.	0.903
SM1-2 I chose to come to China because it is well-known for its education quality.	0.886
SM1-3 I came to China to study so that I may go as far as I can in my educational career.	0.888
SM2-1 Before I came to China, I heard that China was a land of opportunity for students like me to work while studying.	0.912
SM2-2 During my study in China, I have already tried to find a job.	0.777
SM2-3 I need usually to get a job to help finance my study in China.	0.856
SM2-4 I wanted a course of study that allows me to gain work experience while studying.	0.845
SM3-1 Before I came to China, I believed that it would be possible for me to work in China after graduation.	0.866
SM3-2 I intend to find a job in China after the graduation.	0.759
SM3-3 I chose China as the country of my study abroad, because it is a safe place.	0.830
SM4-1 I chose China as the country of my study abroad, because it is a fun place.	0.846
SM4-2 I came to China because I believed that it is possible to meet people from all over the world.	0.862
SM4-3 I have visited many places in China while I study there.	0.813
SM4-4 I have travelled to other countries as a China international student passport holder.	0.898
PR1-1 The teacher determines the students' activities	0.834
PR1-2 The students can determine their own activities.	0.825
PR1-3 S/He is a good leader.	0.710
PR1-4 S/he gives us a lot of free time in class.	0.560
PR1-5 S/He is suspicious.	0.785
PR1-6 S/He seems uncertain.	0.657
PR1-7 S/He is strict.	0.566
PR2-1 The teacher shows approval of the students and their behavior.	0.753
PR2-2 The teacher shows disapproval of the students and their behavior.	0.804
PR2-3 S/He is someone we can depend on.	0.772
PR2-4 If we have something to say s/he will listen.	0.659
PR2-5 S/He gets angry.	0.710
D1-1 I feel passionate about my learning.	0.808
D1-2 I am able to reduce distractions during the period of time I have set aside for studying.	0.800
D1-3 I am able to reduce interruptions during the period of time I have set aside for studying.	0.761
D1-4 I keep my goals in sight at all times.	0.721
D2-1 I have my clear goals that I aspire to achieve.	0.810
D2-2 I set high expectations for myself.	0.711
D2-3 I feel like I have a purpose.	0.724
D2-4 I prepare for my classes.	0.695
D3-1 I feel in control of what academic results I achieve at university.	0.734
D3-2 I believe that I have the ability to perform at high level in my studies.	0.746
D3-3 I do mind how long it takes me to finish my degree.	0.538

Item	Outer Loading
D4-1 I like to create a routine for each of the subjects I study in a semester to keep me moving forward.	0.677
D4-2 I split my workload into small chunks to progress my projects step by step rather than waiting to start work just before something is due.	0.659
D5-1 When I manage my time better, I perform better.	0.698
D5-2 I am spending enough time on studying.	0.723
D5-3 I am on time to my classes	0.737
SS1-1 My lecturer had a thorough knowledge of the subject content.	0.845
SS1-2 My lecturer provided opportunities to ask questions.	0.898
SS1-3 My lecturer treated me with respect.	0.844
SS2-1 I knew how I was going to be assessed.	0.887
SS2-2 The way I was assessed was a fair test of my skills.	0.833
SS2-3 I was assessed at appropriate intervals.	0.856
SS3-1 My study developed my problem-solving skills	0.870
SS3-2 My study helped me develop my ability to work as a team member.	0.704
SS3-3 My study improved my skills in written communication.	0.870
SS3-4 My study helped me to develop the ability to plan my own work.	0.791
SS3-5 As a result of my study, I feel more confident about tackling unfamiliar problems.	0.808
SP1-1 Knowledge, learning and mastery of general principles	0.785
SP1-2 Continues learning, and intellectual curiosity (Learning)	0.803
SP1-3 Artistic appreciation and curiosity (Artistic)	0.851
SP2-1 Multicultural appreciation	0.787
SP2-2 Leadership	0.764
SP2-3 Interpersonal Skills	0.760
SP2-4 Social Responsibility, citizenship, and involvement	0.592
SP3-1 Physical and Psychological Health	0.852
SP3-2 Career Orientation	0.756
SP3-3 Adaptability and life skills	0.861
SP3-4 Perseverance	0.859
SP3-5 Ethics and Integrity	0.588

Source: Research Data (2022)

All constructs have the capacity to undergo additional reliability testing, according to the findings of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) test. A good model is required to have AVE > 0.50 [49]. The following table shows the AVE values in this study.

Table 4: Average Variance Extracted Value

Variable	AVE
Student Motivation (X1)	0.729
Personal Relationship (X2)	0.517
Discipline (X3)	0.510
Student Satisfaction (Y)	0.703
Student Performance (Z)	0.603

Source: Research Data (2022)

Testing the model's reliability is the final step in evaluating the outer model to make sure there are no measurement-related issues. Utilizing Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability indicators, the reliability test was conducted. the construct has strong reliability, the questionnaire used as a tool in this study is reliable, or the latent variable values have Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha > 0.70 as seen in the table below.

Table 5: Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Student Motivation (X1)	0.971	0.974
Personal Relationship (X2)	0.913	0.926
Discipline (X3)	0.936	0.943
Student Satisfaction (Y)	0.957	0.963
Student Performance (Z)	0.938	0.947

Source: Research Data (2022)

Through a bootstrap procedure, the predicted value for all path relationship in the structural model are significant, as shown in the below table.

Table 6: Hypothesis Result

Variable	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T-Statistic	P Value
SM→SS	0.427	0.403	0.163	2.618	0.009
PR→SS	0.305	0.281	0.169	1.982	0.035
D→SS	1.414	1.372	0.167	8.464	0.000
SM→SP	0.301	0.332	0.176	2.715	0.007
PR→SP	0.126	0.133	0.161	2.780	0.005
D→SP	0.399	0.372	0.176	2.263	0.024
SS→SP	0.333	0.331	0.138	2.413	0.016
SM→SS→SP	0.142	0.135	0.072	1.969	0.050
PR→SS→SP	0.102	0.390	0.069	1.966	0.043
D→SS→SP	0.417	0.466	0.189	2.494	0.013

Source: Research Data (2022)

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. The Direct Influence of Student Motivation on Student Satisfaction

According to the findings of this study, student motivation has a direct and considerable beneficial impact on student satisfaction. This demonstrates the student motivation that the CNY Agency provides in order to raise student satisfaction. A short-term attitude that results from an assessment of a student's educational experiences, services, and facilities is known as student satisfaction. Prior to the development of higher education-specific satisfaction models, it was measured using common satisfaction frameworks[10]. The evaluation of a student's academic experience leads to an assessment of the short-term attitude of students' satisfaction. Students' high levels of motivation will also improve their level of satisfaction. The findings of various authors' studies [12][50][51] confirm this, and as a result, student motivation will have an impact on student satisfaction

4.2. The Direct Influence of Personal Relationships on Student Satisfaction

The findings of this study reveal that interpersonal relationships directly and significantly improve student happiness at CNY Agency. This demonstrates how a good personal connection was made to raise student satisfaction. Additionally, this indicates that interpersonal ties have a significant impact on student satisfaction, which is referred to be a short-term attitude coming from appraising students' educational experiences [10]. Therefore, a person's level of satisfaction will rise the better their personal connections develop. Another author [36] also supports the result of this study

4.3. The Direct Effect of Discipline on Student Satisfaction

The results of this study show that at CNY Agency, discipline directly and significantly increases student satisfaction. To improve student satisfaction, this demonstrates the high degree of discipline. Another aspect of discipline is the understanding and readiness of a person to adhere to all applicable laws and social standards. When a student is accountable, has a positive attitude, behaves appropriately, and takes appropriate action while adhering to all rules at the school, this is a sign of good student discipline. Among the university's key goals are improving services and controlling student satisfaction. Actually, the reason there are so many complaints is a result of how poorly institutions treat their customers and also how low student satisfaction. According to the findings of earlier authors' study, students who are well-behaved will be more motivated [52] [53]

4.4. The Direct Influence of Student Motivation on Student Performance

According to the study's findings, CNY Agency students perform better when they are motivated to succeed. This demonstrates how the high levels of motivation the CNY Agency developed in its students led to excellent student performance. Indonesian students who have been motivated to pursue higher education on scholarships from the Chinese government anticipate satisfaction if their goal of studying in China actually happens. Student Motivation has a significant impact on student performance, according to research done in China [54]. The findings of earlier authors provide as evidence for this [54][55]

4.5. The Direct Influence of Personal Relationships on Student Performance

The study's conclusions show that CNY Agency students perform better when they are engaged to others. This demonstrates that establishing strong personal relationships may also result in improved student performance. Performance may be seen as an achievement, demonstrating activity or conduct and completing the tasks that it has been assigned. This finding is consistent with serious research on the subject. [35][36][37][38][39].

4.6. The Direct Effect of Discipline on Student Performance

According to the study's findings, discipline at the CNY Agency directly and significantly improves students' academic achievement. This demonstrates that having a strong sense of discipline may result in improved student performance. Achieving goals and objectives requires strict school discipline. Additionally, it is essential in helping students and teachers develop a feeling of responsibility [56]. Therefore, if students are dedicated and well-

organized, their performance will also improve. Discipline will impact student performance, as shown by the results of earlier scholars' study [57][58][59].

4.7. The Direct Effect of Student Satisfaction on Student Performance

The results of the study show that student satisfaction at the CNY Agency directly and significantly improves students' academic performance. This demonstrates that the CNY Agency provides the satisfaction of its students, which leads to strong student performance. There have been numerous interactions to obtain the necessary information during the learning process that a particular student has experienced. Since student satisfaction can influence student performance, the findings of this study support those of earlier researchers[60][61]

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines how student motivation, interpersonal relationships, discipline, and student satisfaction might improve Indonesian students' performance in China. Students sent by CNY Agency study at various Chinese universities. The analysis method used is SEM-PLS using PLS 3.0 software. The following conclusions regarding this research can be drawn from the analysis and discussion in the previous chapter :

1. The agency's managerial skills affect improving student performance. To optimize student performance, the CNY Agency needs to improve its managerial skills, including: conceptual skills, namely understanding and operating organizations, interpersonal relationship skills, namely skills to work together, motivate and lead; technical skills, namely skills in using knowledge, methods, techniques, and equipment to complete specific tasks.
2. Paying attention to student motivation is essential. Motivation can come from outside the student; determining where to study requires encouragement and motivation. With the agency, it can help students get motivated to determine the best place to study. Therefore, CNY Agency must provide detailed information with a clear picture to increase student motivation.
3. Maintaining a good personal relationship between students and lecturers is essential. Lecturers and students may have a different argument because of very different personalities, styles, expectations, and perspectives on learning. The interaction between lecturers and students is regular and significant to achieving common goals. However, each lecturer displays certain behaviors, which differ from his peers, and students may or may not appreciate it. On the other hand, some lecturers specifically like or dislike the behavior of some students.
4. Discipline is an important thing that must be applied. Disciplines are usually used to denote specific knowledge, research, and education areas. Discipline is to train through teaching or training. Therefore, discipline is closely related to the training process carried out by those who provide direction and guidance in teaching activities.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Researchers offer some recommendations, particularly those relevant to further study, based on the study that has already been conducted and discussed earlier. For CNY organization: Although CNY Agency students do quite good, there are few areas that still need improvement. In order to increase performance, apart from increasing motivation, Discipline and maintaining relationships, it is also necessary to increase other factors. For Scholars: Future researchers are likely to add factors not included in this study. Additionally, a discussion of organizations other than the CNY Agency for International Education might be more extensive. The performance of Indonesian students studying in other countries than China should also be studied.

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